

The Application of Stem Cells in the Recovery of Lost Motor and Sensory Function Due to Spinal Cord Injury

Liam Kerner

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Abstract– The complex yet fragile anatomy of the spinal cord is made up of cells that are unable to reproduce or regenerate themselves. Consequently, spinal cord injuries (SCI) are horrific and life-altering injuries that pose many burdens on patients and families of those living with the condition [1]. Currently, there are no widely used or accepted treatment options for SCI. However, new research and discoveries have made some promising findings for using stem cells to treat SCI. The spinal cord is a fragile organ in the central nervous system (CNS) that is responsible for providing motor and sensory functions throughout the body. Following a spinal cord injury, numerous vital pieces of the spinal cord are lost or damaged. Without these essential pieces of the spinal cord, which include neurons, axons, and oligodendrocytes, a person is unable to possess many sensory and motor functions throughout their body [31]. Fortunately, many animal models and clinical trials have had promising results in regenerating these vital organs and restoring motor and sensory function to patients suffering from SCI; nevertheless, they are still in the early stages of development. This review will provide details on the current stages and future progression of using stem cells to treat spinal cord injuries.

I. Introduction

Spinal cord injuries are devastating and life-altering conditions that affect approximately 282,000 people in the United States alone - with about 17,000 new cases each year [1]. In the United States, the main causes of SCIs are motor vehicle accidents and traumatic falls; some other causes of spinal cord injuries include sporting accidents, gunshot wounds, disease, surgical accidents, etc. [2]. Although the fatality rate of an SCI is relatively low at just under 4%, the economic effects of an SCI constitute a very large burden on an individual living with the condition. This cost generally runs around 1.5 to 3.0 million dollars per individual [3]. This cost covers medical bills, treatments such as physical therapy, and day-to-day-life accommodations [3]. Economic and physical burdens are not the only devastation caused by the condition, for a person living with an SCI, their quality of life can be dramatically decreased as well [3]. For someone living with an SCI that resulted in paralysis (caused by increased traumatic damage to nerve fibers near the injury), these statistics are much larger. Paralysis occurs in around 1.7% of the U.S. population [2].

SCI can be classified into two groups based on the level of muscles and sensory control allowed after the injury: these categories are incomplete and complete. An incomplete SCI allows little neural communication between the brain and the rest of the

body. Incomplete injury typically allows for some sensory function and sometimes muscle control below the affected area after the injury takes place [2]. The other level of function is classified as a complete SCI, which does not allow for any nerve communication below the affected site leaving all motor functions to be depleted [2]. SCI also can lead to many later health complications, which even further decrease a patient's quality of life. If the injury is left untreated either moments or after long periods following the initial injury an incomplete injury can progress into a complete injury [2]. If either of the variations is left untreated major health concerns may arise. These concerns can include internal issues such as breathing complications, which are likely to develop. Respiratory difficulty also leads to a higher risk for infection to occur, such as the development of pneumonia [6]. All of these conditions are caused by traumatic SCI.

Current methods used to treat the effects of an SCI are quite limited; they also take time to become effective. Some current treatments exist for patients who have not experienced full paralysis and include surgery to remove fluid from the injury site, or realignment tactics to revert the spine to its original position [5]. People with spinal cord injuries also benefit from rehab practices such as physical therapy, which aim to help strengthen the muscles affected by the injury. These methods assist patients in regaining muscle control [5]. For patients who have complete spinal cord injury resulting in paralysis (or if their incomplete SCI develops into paralysis), there are currently no widely used or accepted treatments. Because of the apparent risks of incomplete SCI developing into complete SCI due to a lack of a widely used treatment option, the urgent need for fast and reliable care arises, which may entail stem cell therapy.

II. The Spinal Cord

The spinal cord is an essential organ that is a part of the central nervous system (CNS) [10]. The spinal cord is a vital part of the body's structure and is responsible for sending motor and sensory commands to other parts of the body to and from the brain [13]. Despite the spinal cord's fragile makeup, it houses many crucial structures that allow the organ to function properly. Externally, the spinal cord is protected by the vertebral column. The exterior of the spinal cord is further secured by 3 layers of membrane: the dura mater, the arachnoid, and the innermost pia mater [16]. The length of the spinal cord is divided into 4 levels: cervical nerves, thoracic nerves, lumbar nerves, and sacral nerves [34].

Figure 1. Levels of the spinal cord [34]

Internally, the spinal cord is composed of two layers consisting of gray matter and white matter [11]. Gray matter encompasses three layers: the dorsal horns, intermediate gray, and ventral horns [10]. Located within the three layers are valuable types of neurons [10]. These neurons include motor neurons, sympathetic preganglionic neurons, and sensory neurons. The responsibility of these neurons is to help communicate motor and sensory functions around the body. The white matter of the spinal cord encapsulates the gray matter located in the center and is divided by the lateral spinal nucleus [10]. Contained in the white matter are axons [11]. Axons are part of nerve cells and are in charge of sending signals that allow the spinal cord to communicate with the rest of the body [11]. Axons greatly vary in length and can be as small as a millimeter and can extend up to a full meter depending on their function [17]. While located inside the spinal cord's white matter, axons are surrounded by an insulation substance called myelin [17]. Myelin helps the axons, located in the nerve cells, send controls over long distances throughout the body which is a vital contribution to sensory and motor function [17]. Furthermore, myelin-producing oligodendrocytes are vital components in the function of axons and the spinal cord [33]. Axons communicate with other neurons using their action potential [12]. Neurons also consist of dendrites where the neurons receive input from various commands, and the cell body where the DNA is housed [17].

Figure 2. Neuron Anatomy [35]

III. Spinal Cord Injury (SCI)

Spinal cord injuries are defined as damage done to the cells and nerves, which are responsible for communicating brain signals. These signals are in charge of motor and sensory functions within the body [2]. As previously mentioned, SCIs can also be classified into two different levels of mobility: incomplete and complete. Spinal cord injuries also vary depending on where the impact occurred on the spinal cord. The different areas of the injury site create variations in the effects of the impairment [7]. The levels of the spinal cord (cervical, thoracic, lumbar, and sacral) also help to further classify SCI severity and the outcomes that would occur after the injury [9].

Each classification level of spinal cord injuries assists professionals in evaluating the severity of a patient's condition. This information assists in maximizing recovery efficiency for SCI patients. Following the occurrence of a SCI, the anatomy of the spinal cord is drastically changed. After a SCI, different stages of degeneration occur in the spinal cord, these stages can be divided into primary and secondary injuries [18]. The primary injury involves direct mechanical trauma to the spinal cord. This can involve vertebral column fractures, which can further lead to the disruption of axons, blood vessels, and cell membranes (dura mater, arachnoid, innermost pia mater) [18]. Further primary injury can include the breakdown of the myelin, which can depreciate motor and sensory function further due to the loss of axonal communication in the body [31]. Furthermore, after primary injury, the loss of oligodendrocytes and astrocytes further promotes the loss of sensory and motor functions [33]. In addition, spinal cord trauma can result in axonal degeneration and necrosis (cell death) [19]. These two side effects of SCI are partially what causes the loss of sensory and motor function due to the deprivation of neuron structure and communication [19,20]. With these initial events taking place, energy is lost in the neurons leading to complete nerve death [18]. Secondary injury is also apparent after primary injury. The effects of secondary injury include vascular damage, scar formation in the spinal cord, and progressive nerve cell death [18].

IV. Current Treatments

After the initial SCI, it is vital to disable any further spinal movements to eliminate the chances of injury progression. After the response to the injury, there are a variety of treatment options that can be performed to help stop further damage and allow the acute injury to be resolved [21]. These treatments can include surgery, spine stabilization, and administration of medication. Unfortunately, there are currently no widely used or accepted treatments for patients to completely reverse the damage caused to the spinal cord [22]. However, rehabilitation practices help patients improve function; unfortunately, these practices will continue to leave patients to experience motor and sensory function impairment.

V. Stem Cells

Stem cells are a unique category of cells that have the ability to specialize into several other types of cells within the body [26]. The classification of stem cells is based on their renewal abilities and origins. For a cell to be classified as a stem cell, it needs to possess the ability to self-renew (replicate) and the ability to differentiate into functional tissue [23]. Pluripotent stem cells, also known as embryonic stem cells (ESC), and induced pluripotent stem cells derived from young embryos [23].

Figure 3. Stem Cell Classifications [37]

These embryos are at their blastocyst stage when they contain the type of cell harvested for ESC transplant, cells of the inner mass. Unlike embryonic cells, somatic stem cells (or adult stem cells) are classified as multipotent, meaning that they are more limited in their development into other types of cells, unlike pluripotent cells [26]. Somatic stem cells are found in smaller numbers in adult tissues such as bone marrow and fat [24].

VI. The Application of Stem Cells in Spinal Cord Injury Treatment

After the occurrence of a spinal cord injury, the body deploys its natural defense system containing

endogenous neural stem cells (NSC) to the injury site in an attempt to repair damaged tissue [27]. Although the body's repair mechanism releases NSCs to the lesion site, the multipotent behavior of the cells fails to regenerate sensory and motor functions lost after SCI (28). This natural failure to regain the body's motor and sensory function shows the invaluable nature that stem cells may provide to the treatment of SCI patients.

Trial Location/ Sponsor	Spinal Cord Injury Classification	Stem Cell Therapy Used	Number of Patients in Trial	Trial Phase
Asterias Biotherapeutics (CA, USA)	Spinal Cord Injury	Human-ESC- derived oligodendrocyte precursor cells	13	Phase 1/2
Neuralstem Inc. (MD, USA)	Chronic Spinal Cord Injury	Fetal- derived neural stem cells	4	Phase 1
Stem Cells Inc. (CA, USA)	Cervical Spinal Cord Injury	Human CNS stem cells	50	Phase 2
Stem Cells Inc. (CA, USA)	Thoracic Spinal Cord Injury	Human CNS stem cells	12	Phase 1/2
Wroclaw Medical University (Poland)	Spinal Cord Injury	Olfactory ensheathing cells, autologous	10	Phase 1

Figure 4. SCI treatment trials using stem cell therapy [36].

A. Embryonic Stem Cells

Embryonic stem cells are some of the most versatile and most debated types of stem cells. ESCs are obtained from the inner mass of an embryo during its blastocyst stage and are deployed directly into the body at the injured area of the SCI via an injection [30]. ESCs have great potential in the field of regenerative medicine due to their continuous renewal abilities, which are able to complete 300-400 population renewal cycles [38]. Due to their pluripotent behavior, ESCs are an ideal solution for regenerating damaged neurons and glial cells (support neurons and their functions) affected by spinal cord trauma [31].

Many variations of ESCs exist, for one, ESC-derived definitive neural cells have shown promising results in animal models by promoting myelin growth, which is vital in the regeneration of lost axons from SCI [31]. Furthermore, after ESC transplantation into the spinal cord, the cells were able to myelinate axons in an animal model promoting faster communication of neural transmission across fibers [28]. Due to the promotion of axonal growth, the restoration of the spinal cord, and lost sensory and motor function, myelin is a key ingredient in spinal cord repair [28]. This leaves a need for increased myelin production.

Fortunately, many studies have shown in animal models that ESCs can also differentiate into myelin-producing oligodendrocytes (a type of glial cell) for SCI patients [32]. The increase and production of myelin allows for the vital re-isolation and rapid transmission of electrical currents throughout the body [32]. These electrical currents are vital in regaining sensory and motor function. Alongside the myelin-producing abilities and pluripotent behavior, ESC-derived neural lineage cells allow axons to pass through the chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan, which

previously was a large barrier for axonal regeneration in the spinal cord; this further supports how ESCs may be a viable SCI treatment option [31].

Many recent studies have shown ESC treatment potential, such as a study conducted in 2016. This study exhibited patients having restored body functions after using ESCs to reverse SCI damage [32]. Despite the positive impact of using ESCs to treat SCI, there are a few drawbacks when it comes to using this method. For one, the origin of the ESCs is highly debated as the cells are taken from the blastocyst stage of human embryos. In addition to the debates, ESCs have been shown to possess tumor formation abilities due to the pluripotent nature of the cells [31].

B. Neural Stem Cells (NSC)

Neural stem cells are a variety of multipotent stem cells that have the ability to differentiate into neurons and other neuroglial cells [33]. NSCs are divided into two variations: endogenous and exogenous [33]. Endogenous NSCs are already found in the body's CNS and are a part of the natural defense mechanism that is deployed after the occurrence of a traumatic SCI. Following a SCI, endogenous NSCs rush to the lesion site, and differentiate into high volumes of astrocytes and smaller amounts of oligodendrocytes. When the endogenous NSCs reach the lesion site they provide neurotrophic effects and stabilize tissue integrity in the spinal cord [33]. Unfortunately, without human intervention, these endogenous NSCs are unable to reverse damages done to the spinal cord or improve motor and sensory function after injury [33]. Fortunately, there are a large number of studies being conducted, which aim to help further employ endogenous NSCs to help repair lost function after a SCI [27]. Furthermore, ependymal cells are widely used and accepted NSCs already found in the spinal cord. Due to their multipotent behavior, they have been shown effective in mice models to divide into effective astrocytes, oligodendrocytes, and neurons [33].

On the other hand, exogenous NSCs are harvested outside of the spinal cord and are used for cell transplant therapies unlike endogenous NSCs [33]. Exogenous NSCs have some similar characteristics to endogenous NSCs, such as they are able to self-renew, can proliferate, and possess the ability to differentiate into other types of cells [33]. Exogenous NSCs are sourced from the extraction of CNS tissues or by direct or indirect reprogramming of somatic cells [33]. For exogenous NSCs, once injected or deployed to the injury site, moderate inflammation and immune microenvironments produce growth to support axonal growth. Exogenous NSCs have the ability to differentiate into neuronal and neuroglial lineages [33]. These behaviors of exogenous NSCs are an indicator that they are a viable treatment option for SCI repair. In addition, NSCs drastically increase myelin production within the spinal cord. This is due to the migration of NSCs to the cystic cavity and the differentiation ability of the cells into oligodendrocytes proving as a vital component in spinal cord repair [33].

Conclusion

In brief, the devastating effects of SCI such as the loss of sensory and motor function, as well as the decreased quality of life, may be able to be treated using embryonic or neural stem cells. Embryonic stem cells are a viable treatment option for restoring lost motor and sensory function due to their unique pluripotent behaviors. The ESC's ability to regenerate axons combined with myelin-producing oligodendrocytes showed full recoveries for SCI in animal models and in some early human clinical trials. Conversely, ethical issues surrounding the embryonic origin of the cells are highly debated and jeopardize the usage of ESCs in a clinical setting; current testing has shown ESCs to be a feasible treatment method for SCI patients and future research may help this treatment option become more accepted and widely used. Neural stem cells - both endogenous and exogenous - have also shown promising results in treating SCI. Due to the comprehensive studies on NSCs, by viewing their unique behaviors and natural deployment, combined with their multipotent nature, they are promising treatments in repairing damaged and lost axons as well as maintaining stability in the spinal cord. In summary, with the development of future trials and more conclusive research, stem cells have a great potential to treat spinal cord injury.

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